

Dark Energy Survey Gold

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Back in 2018 the Dark Energy Survey (DES) released DR1, the images and catalogs from the first three years of survey operations (Y3) with the Dark Energy Camera (DECam) on the Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope at Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory. Over the past several months, 30 papers are in the publication stream that collectively constrain cosmological parameters based on DR1. This major undertaking has required years of development to generate precise estimates of photometric redshift and shape for each galaxy. These, and many other value-added products derived from DR1, were made public on 12 January 2022 to support the conclusions of the cosmology papers. The DES Collaboration has documented the methods and the data products for what we call “Y3 Gold” in the paper [Sevilla-Noarbe et al. 2021, ApJS, 254, 24](#). The release is hosted by the National Center for Supercomputer Applications. Much information to help users can be found at [DES Data Management: Y3 Cosmology Data Release](#).

While the data products in the Y3 Gold release support the DES cosmology analyses, we expect that they will have general utility for many other astrophysical applications. The photometric depth, uniformity, and precision are improved over previous releases, as are the object classifications.

Figure 1. The Milky Way arches high over the Blanco 4-meter telescope at Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (CTIO) in Chile. The Blanco 4-meter Telescope began operating in 1976, providing astronomers with a world-class observatory in the southern hemisphere, and it continues to produce cutting-edge science. The Blanco is currently equipped with the Dark Energy Camera (DECam), a state-of-the-art 520-megapixel camera which completed the five-year Dark Energy Survey in early 2019. DECam continues with an expanded mission and is providing astronomers with a powerful tool for studying dark energy, exoplanets and more. Credit: CTIO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/D. Munizaga

Science Highlights

In addition to the wide-field data products, the Y3 Gold release includes deep-field images and catalogs based on the fields that had been visited weekly for discovery of supernovae. Including the area also covered in near-infrared bands by VISTA, the release contains 8-band photometry ($ugrizJHKS$) over 5.88 square degrees with an exposure of at least 10 times that of the wide-field survey.

In summary, the wide-field release features the following:

- 390 million objects with $grizY$ photometry in nearly 5000 deg²
- S/N ~ 10 for extended objects to $i \sim 23.0$ AB
- i -band PSF 0.9" FWHM
- photometric uniformity < 0.003 magnitude
- astrometric residuals compared to Gaia DR2: 0.158" rms

Figure 2. DECam on the Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope. Credit: Reidar Hahn, Fermilab

Figure 3. Mass map based on the weak lensing signal, where the circles show the positions of independently identified rich clusters of galaxies. These data reveal a correlation between the visible mass (the clusters) and the dark matter (detected via weak lensing). Credit: N. Jeffrey et al. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, Volume 505, 4626

NSF's NOIRLab

The interacting galaxy pair NGC 1512 and NGC 1510 take center stage in this image from the Dark Energy Camera on the Victor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope at Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory, a Program of NSF's NOIRLab. NGC 1512 has been in the process of merging with its smaller galactic neighbor for some 400 million years, and this drawn-out interaction has ignited waves of star formation and warped both galaxies. *Credit: Dark Energy Survey/DOE/FNAL/DECam/CTIO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA*